

Synthesis of aryl substituted azomethine complexes of iron-, cobalt- and copper(II)

Rajendra Prasad^{a*}, P. P. Thankachan^a, Molly T. Thomas^b and Rajiv Pathak^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667, India

E-mail : rajenfcy@rurkiu.ernet.in

^bSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, India

Manuscript received 16 March 2000, revised 6 July 2000, accepted 26 August 2000

Pseudotetrahedral and pseudooctahedral complexes of the types $[ML_2Cl_2]$, $[M(L-L)Cl_2]$, $[ML_4Cl_2]$ and $[M(L-L)_2Cl_2]$ (where, L = $C_6H_5CH=NC_6H_5$ or $C_6H_5CH=NC_6H_5-4-COOC_2H_5$; L-L = $C_6H_5CH=N-C_6H_4-2-N=CHC_6H_5$; M = Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II}) have been synthesized. The complexes undergo octahedral to tetrahedral conversions in acetone and vice versa in ethanol solutions.

The azomethines are very weak bases ($pK_{a1} \sim 5-8$) and thereby are supposed to possess poor coordination tendency. This coupled with their proclivity for hydrolysis have been primarily responsible for study of only a very limited number of transition metal complexes with azomethine only donor ligands¹. This is despite the fact that quite a vast number of azomethines with a variety of C and N substituent groups have been synthesized and studied. Most of the azomethine complexes so far studied involve either additional donor atoms as in salicyldimine (Salen) and its analogs² or those with conjugated diimine groups, viz. *o*-benzoquinonediimine (bqdi)³, glyoxal-bis-(methylimine) (gmi), biacetyl-bis(methylimine) (bmi)⁴ etc. In the former type of complexes, the binding capability of the additional phenoxide-O donor has been exploited to impart stability to the complex. whereas in the latter, the π -backbonding tendency of the ligand has been exploited.

Since the azomethines are soft bases and also possess moderate π -acid capability through their π^* orbitals, it is expected that they could give reasonably stable complexes with soft acid metal cations particularly those capable of π -backdonation. Thus in continuation of our earlier studies on azomethine complexes⁵, we herein report the synthesis and characterization of ternary complexes of benzylideneaniline (BAAN), 4-(benzylideneimino)ethylbenzoate (BAEB) and *N,N'*-bis(benzylidene)-1,2-diaminobenzene (BDB) with Fe^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions. These azomethines belong to three different classes, viz. simple, with electron-withdrawing substituent and with two disparate azomethine groups having benzene ring spacer, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Pseudotetrahedral complexes (sl. nos. 1-9) and pseudo-

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of complexes^c

Sl. no.	Compd.	Λ_{m1}^a $\Omega^{-1}cm^2$ mol^{-1}	μ_{eff}^b B.M.	$\nu_{C=N}$ cm^{-1}	λ_{max} , nm (ϵ_{max} , $mol^{-1}cm^2$) ^c
1.	[Fe(BAAN) ₂ Cl ₂]	6	5.21	1600	260 (2.2×10^4), 360 (sh)
2.	[Co(BAAN) ₂ Cl ₂]	12	4.29	1615	280 (2.2×10^4), 590 (4.0×10^5), 695 (6.0×10^5)
3.	[Cu(BAAN) ₂ Cl ₂]	12	1.71	1600	285 (2.0×10^4)
4.	[Fe(BAEB) ₂ Cl ₂]	22	5.15	1600	295 (2.4×10^4), 360 (sh)
5.	[Co(BAEB) ₂ Cl ₂]	16	4.20	1615	300 (2.0×10^4), 595 (4.2×10^5), 688 (6.0×10^5)
6.	[Cu(BAEB)Cl ₂]	19	1.79	1600	295 (2.2×10^4)
7.	[Fe(BDB)Cl ₂]	10	5.28	1620	290 (2.0×10^4), 320 (sh)
8.	[Co(BDB)Cl ₂]	15	4.19	1618	288 (2.1×10^4), 595 (3.0×10^5), 677 (5.0×10^5)
9.	[Cu(BDB)Cl ₂]	18	1.68	1618	286 (2.0×10^4)
10.	[Fe(BAAN) ₄ Cl ₂]	8	4.81	1600	285 (2.8×10^4), 540 (25)
11.	[Co(BAAN) ₄ Cl ₂]	5	3.82	1610	282 (2.8×10^4), 530 (30)
12.	[Cu(BAAN) ₄ Cl ₂]	10	1.88	1600	285 (2.9×10^4), 500 (55), 567 (45)
13.	[Fe(BAEB) ₄ Cl ₂]	10	5.00	1605	300 (2.7×10^4), 555 (30)
14.	[Co(BAEB) ₄ Cl ₂]	8	3.93	1605	300 (2.8×10^4), 535 (20)
15.	[Cu(BAEB) ₄ Cl ₂]	15	1.85	1605	295 (2.8×10^4), 500 (40), 570 (35)
16.	[Fe(BDB) ₂ Cl ₂]	9	5.09	1605	290 (2.8×10^4), 454 (12)
17.	[Co(BDB) ₂ Cl ₂]	14	3.95	1605	288 (2.7×10^4), 525 (15)
18.	[Cu(BDB) ₂ Cl ₂]	12	1.90	1605	288 (2.7×10^4), 452 (12), 485 (10)

*All compounds gave satisfactory metal, Cl and N analyses.

^aAt 1×10^{-2} M in acetone for sl. nos. 1-9 and in EtOH having 0.1 M free ligand for sl. nos. 10-18. ^bAt 295 K. ^cElectronic spectra of sl. nos. 1-9 in acetone and of sl. nos. 10-18 in EtOH.

octahedral complexes (sl. nos. 10–18) (Table 1) were obtained as major products from acetone and methanol solutions, respectively. Ligand BAEB takes longer time to react than BAAN and BDB and also reaches to completion to a lesser extent. It has been found that both the tetrahedral and octahedral complexes exist in equilibrium in ethanol but the equilibrium lies more towards formation of the octahedral complexes. The poorer activity of the BAEB vis-a-vis BAAN and BDB is possibly due to its weaker basicity as an electron-withdrawing group is present on the benzene ring attached to imino nitrogen. Yields of the reactions varied with the nature of the ligand (BDB > BAAN > BAEB) as well as with the nature of the metal ions. Iron has the highest tendency to form octahedral complexes whereas cobalt(II) has highest tendency to give tetrahedral complexes. All these complexes are appreciably stable at room temperature in dry state. However, in solution they undergo decompositions to varying extent depending on the nature of solvent. The complexes are paramagnetic and their magnetic susceptibilities are in conformity with their structural types. Conductance ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ concentration) values of the complexes sl. nos. 1–9 in acetone and of sl. nos. 10–18 in ethanol (in presence of 0.1 M free ligand) exhibit their non-electrolytic nature⁶.

IR spectra : IR data of complexes are listed in Table 1. All complexes exhibit one band at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N) vibration. This band, when compared to that observed in the free ligands⁷ (BAAN at 1626, BEAB at 1625 and BDB at 1600 cm^{-1}) reveals shifts towards lower frequency side upon complexation with reduced intensity. It has been observed that binding of a third substituent to the azomethine N, giving azomethinium salt, causes an upward shift⁸ of ca. 30 cm^{-1} . Also the coordination with metal ion lowers conjugative interaction of C=N with the benzene rings which would cause similar upward shift, whereas $M \rightarrow$ (azomethine) π -back-donation would cause lowering of the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ frequency. Hence, in these complexes there exists considerable $M \rightarrow L$ π -interaction. The apparent upward shift of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands in the BDB complexes is contrary to the expected trend. This is because upon complexation BDB forms a five-membered metallacyclic ring in which the C=N bonds are attached *exo* to the ring. Thus like in pyrrolidinium salts ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ ca. 1688 cm^{-1})⁹ these bands should have been observed at much higher frequency, however, the observed shifts are significantly less and are indicative of $M \rightarrow L$ π -back-interaction. The conjugated α, α' -diimines, upon metal complexation exhibit downward $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ frequency shift of ca. 120 cm^{-1} {e.g. $\text{CH}_3\text{-N=CH-CH=N-CH}_3$ (gmi) 1650 cm^{-1} and $[\text{Fe}(\text{gmi})_3]^{2+}$ 1530 cm^{-1} }¹⁶, due to π -back-donation which is far greater than the ap-

parent downward shift in the azomethine complexes, indicating a comparatively weaker π -interaction. MNDO calculations show that the π^* -LUMO in gmi, having energy 0.123 eV, are more favourably disposed for $M \rightarrow L$ π -interaction than the π^* -LUMO's in BAAN, BEAB and BDB (with energies 1.168 to 1.512 eV). Also the bite size in BDB (calcd. 2.69 Å) is marginally shorter than in gmi (calcd. 2.86 Å).

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectral data of all these complexes is listed in Table 1. All complexes exhibit an intense absorption band in the range 300–360 nm. As similar bands are observed in the corresponding free ligands also⁷ so in conformity with their assignments these bands could be attributed to have originated from intraligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. Green cobalt complexes obtained from acetone solutions exhibit two additional bands in the visible region at 590, 695 for BAAN, 595, 688 for BEAB and at 595, 677 nm for BDB. The position and the intensity of these bands are in agreement with analogous quinoline complex $[\text{Co}(\text{quin})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ which exhibits bands at 582, 635 nm^{11,12} and therefore, could be assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ and ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ transitions. The corresponding iron and copper complexes obtained from acetone solutions do not exhibit any band in the visible region, instead the UV band at $\sim 290 \text{ nm}$ tails upto 450 nm. Considering the tetrahedral nature of these complexes, the ${}^5E \rightarrow {}^5T_2$ transition in the iron and ${}^2T_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ transitions in the copper complexes are expected to be of much lower energy and thus are expected to fall in the NIR region between 1000 and 2000 nm¹³.

Complexes sl. nos. 10–18, that were obtained by the reaction of metal salts and azomethines in ethanol solution, exhibit bands in the visible region at 400–600 nm (ϵ_{max} 10–20 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), whereas, for complexes sl. nos. 1–9, these bands are much weaker and thus are indicative of more symmetrical environment around the metal ions. The cobalt complex exhibits a broad band at $\sim 530 \text{ nm}$. Analogous isoquinoline complex $[\text{Co}(\text{IQ})_4\text{Cl}_2]$ exhibits bands¹¹ at 507, 531 and 560(sh) nm in CHCl_3 . It seems that the band observed in the cobalt complexes is a composite of three bands arising from ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$. These bands further split due to lowered symmetry of the complex. The corresponding copper complexes exhibit two bands. If they are to be considered as having near octahedral geometry the two bands must have originated from the tetragonally distorted field arising due to the presence of two axial chloride ions¹⁴. In the iron complexes only one band has been observed in the visible region due to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition.

Solution characteristics : Octahedral complexes (sl. nos. 10–18) undergo fast dissociation in non-hydroxylic polar

organic solvents. Purple colored cobalt complexes, when dissolved in acetone, gives blue green solution, the visible spectra of which resemble that of the corresponding tetrahedral complexes. Similarly, the visible spectral bands in the octahedral iron and copper complexes disappear upon dissolving in acetone. Furthermore, the tetrahedral cobalt complexes in dry ethanol give purple solutions which exhibit one band at 500–550 nm and additional bands at ~590, 625 and 695 nm. This spectra seem to be a composite spectra of three species^{13–15} viz. $[\text{CoL}_4(\text{EtOH})_2]^{2+}$, $[\text{CoL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$ (ca. 2 : 1 : 2 molar ratio at 1×10^{-2} M concentration). If an excess (ca. 20 molar times) of free ligand is added to this solution and the mixture is refluxed for 15 min, the 625 nm band disappears and intensities of other bands get tremendously reduced. Analogous changes have been observed for the iron and copper complexes. It seems that complexes undergo following reactions in the solutions,

In ethanol :

and in acetone : $[\text{ML}_4\text{Cl}_2] \longrightarrow [\text{ML}_2\text{Cl}_2] + 2 \text{L}$

Experimental

Benzaldehyde, aniline, *p*-aminobenzoic acid, *o*-phenylenediamine and metal salts $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R. grade) were used as received. $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was freshly prepared by dissolving iron filings in conc. HC. Solvents used were freshly dried and distilled. Azomethines were prepared using literature methods¹⁶.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and UV-visible spectra on a Beckman 26 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a PARC 155 magnetometer. Conductance was measured on a Systronics 304 conductivity meter. Metal, nitrogen and chloride were estimated using standard procedures¹⁷.

$[\text{ML}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ complexes ($L = \text{BAAN}, \text{BEAB}$) : A mixture of the ligand (BAAN or BAEB, 8.0 mmol), metal salt (3.0 mmol) and anhydrous CaSO_4 (5.0 g, ~28 mmol) taken in dry acetone (60 ml) was refluxed for 2–3 h until metal salts dissolved completely. The color of the solution changed to dark yellow for iron salt, from green to yellow-brown for copper salt and from blue to green for cobalt salt. It was then cooled, filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate at reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with small quantity of dry benzene and reprecipitated by adding excess of petroleum ether. It was crystallized from benzene/pet. ether and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 , yields 50–60%.

$[\text{M}(\text{BDB})\text{Cl}_2]$ complexes : A mixture of the diimine (BDB; 1.42 g, 5.0 mmol), metal salt (3.0 mmol) and anhydrous CaSO_4 (5.0 g, ~28 mmol) taken in dry acetone (60 ml) was refluxed for 2–3 h until metal salts dissolved completely. The color of the solution changed to dark yellow for iron salt, from green to yellow-brown for copper salt and from blue to green for cobalt salt. It was then cooled, filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate at reduced pressure. The residue was extracted in small quantity of dry benzene and reprecipitated by adding excess of pet. ether. It was crystallized from benzene/pet. ether and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 , yields 50–60%.

$[\text{ML}_4\text{Cl}_2]$ complexes ($L = \text{BAAN}, \text{BEAB}$) : A mixture of the ligand (20 mmol) and metal salt (3 mmol) in absolute dry ethanol (80 ml) was refluxed for 2–6 h. Color of the solution changed to brown-yellow for iron and copper salts and to blue for cobalt salt. It was then filtered, the volume of the filtrate reduced to ~10 ml and cooled at 0° for 5 h. The solid that separated was washed with dry ethanol (2 × 5 ml) and was dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 , yields 40–60%.

$[\text{M}(\text{BDB})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ complexes : A mixture of the diimine (BDB; 2.84 g, 10 mmol) and metal salt (3 mmol) in absolute dry ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. Color of the solution changed to orange-yellow for iron and cobalt salts and to brown for copper salt. It was then filtered, the volume of the filtrate reduced to ~10 ml and cooled at 0° for 5 h. The solid that separated was washed with dry ethanol (2 × 5 ml) and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 , yields 50–70%.

References

1. M. Calligaris and L. Randaccio in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", eds. G. Wilkinson, R. D. Gillard and J. A. McCleverty, Pergamon, London, 1987, Vol. 2; P. Attanasio, A. A. G. Tomlinson and L. Alagna, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 618.
2. A. Kriza, A. Reiss, S. Florea and T. Caproiu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 207; M. Zimmer, D. A. Tocher, G. K. Patra, J. P. Nasker and D. Dutta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 1087; S. Sinha, A. K. Banerjee and B. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 269; G. Parihan and G. Neela, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 713.
3. H. Masui, A. B. P. Lever and E. S. Dodsworth, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **32**, 258.
4. M. J. Balandamer, J. Burgess, J. Faucett, P. Guardado, C. D. Hubbard, S. Nuttall, L. J. S. Prouse, S. Radulovic and D. R. Russel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 1381.
5. R. Pathak and R. Prasad, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1996, **105**, 299.
6. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
7. C. Sandorfy in "The Chemistry of Carbon Nitrogen Double Bond".

Note

- ed. S. Patai, Interscience, London, 1970.
8. N. J. Leonard and J. V. Pauskalis, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 3021; B. Witkop and T. W. Beiler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5589, 5597; B. Witkop and J. B. Patrick, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4474.
 9. O. E. Edwards and T. Singh, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1954, **32**, 465.
 10. E. Bayer and G. Haflinger, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, **99**, 1689.
 11. H. C. A. King, E. Koros and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 4832.
 12. W. L. Darby and L. M. Vallerino, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **48**, 215.
 13. D. M. L. Goodgame, M. Goodgame, M. A. Hitchman and M. J. Weeks, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 635.
 14. J. Reedijk, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1970, **89**, 993.
 15. N. S. Gill and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3997; N. S. Gill, R. S. Nyholm, G. A. Barckey, T. I. Christie and P. O. Pauling, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 188.
 16. A. Lowy and C. G. King, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 625.
 17. "Vogel's Textbook Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", eds. J. Bassett, R. C. Denny, G. H. Jeffery and J. Mendham, ELBS, London, 1978.